

Towards a dispersive calculation of the isospin-breaking corrections to τ data

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Abstract

A reliable calculation of radiative corrections to $\tau \rightarrow \pi\pi\nu_\tau$ decays is an important prerequisite for using hadronic τ decays for a data-driven evaluation of the hadronic-vacuum-polarization contribution to the anomalous magnetic moment of the muon, $a_\mu^{\text{HVP, LO}}[\pi\pi, \tau]$. In Refs. [1, 2] we developed an improved model-independent analysis of these radiative corrections, including, for the first time, effects beyond point-like pions in the evaluation of the loop diagrams. These structure-dependent corrections, implemented via a dispersive representation of the pion form factor, lead to significant changes compared to previous calculations due to enhancements near the $\rho(770)$ resonance.

1 Introduction

The $\tau \rightarrow \pi\pi\nu_\tau$ decay offers an alternative approach to compute the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ cross section necessary for the data-driven estimate of $a_\mu^{\text{HVP, LO}}$. In order to use this τ data approach control over radiative corrections is crucial. The τ -based approach, pioneered in Ref. [3], relies on an isospin rotation from the $\pi^\pm\pi^0$ channel probed in τ decays back to $\pi^+\pi^-$ as required for the two-pion contribution $a_\mu^{\text{HVP, LO}}[\pi\pi]$.

In our work [1, 2], we address an improved calculation of the radiative corrections to $\tau \rightarrow \pi\pi\nu_\tau$. So far, the evaluation of radiative corrections is based on chiral perturbation theory (ChPT) [4, 5] in combination with resonance models [6–11], which makes robust uncertainty quantification difficult, see Ref. [12] (based on Refs. [8, 10, 11, 13, 14]) for a review isospin-breaking (IB) corrections. Most importantly, we consider structure-dependent virtual corrections based on a dispersive representation of the pion form factor. In this context, we pay particular attention to the matching to ChPT, to be able to make the connection to short-distance (SD) contributions as well as lattice QCD [15]. We also revisit the calculation of real corrections, including the singular threshold behavior, and develop a method for a stable numerical evaluation of these corrections down to the two-pion threshold. Finally, we perform fits to the available τ spectral functions from Belle [16], ALEPH [17, 18], CLEO [19], and OPAL [20], to assess the consequences for the IB corrections in a τ -based evaluation of the 2π channel, $a_\mu^{\text{HVP, LO}}[\pi\pi, \tau]$.

At first order in IB, the decay rate can be expressed in the form

$$\frac{d\Gamma[\tau \rightarrow \pi\pi\nu_\tau(\gamma)]}{ds} = S_{\text{EW}}^{\pi\pi} K_\Gamma(s) \beta_{\pi\pi^0}^3 |f_+(s)|^2 G_{\text{EM}}(s), \quad (1)$$

where s is the invariant mass squared of the two-pion pair, and the normalization further involves $K_\Gamma(s) = \frac{\Gamma_e |V_{ud}|^2}{2m_\tau^2} (1 - \frac{s}{m_\tau^2})^2 (1 + \frac{2s}{m_\tau^2})$, with $\Gamma_e \equiv \Gamma[\tau \rightarrow e\nu_\tau\bar{\nu}_e]$, $\text{Br}[\tau \rightarrow e\nu_\tau\bar{\nu}_e] = 17.82(4)\%$ [21, 22], and $V_{ud} = 0.97367(32)$ [21]. We will also use the result of the global fit $\text{Br}[\tau \rightarrow \pi\pi\nu_\tau] = 25.49(9)\%$ [21, 22], including its correlation -0.19 with $\text{Br}[\tau \rightarrow e\nu_\tau\bar{\nu}_e]$.

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Figure 1: Virtual photonic corrections to $\tau \rightarrow \pi\pi\nu_\tau$ in ChPT. Solid lines denote leptons, dashed lines pions, and wiggly lines photons. Not shown are self-energy diagrams and contact terms.

Figure 2: Box diagram in a dispersive approach. The gray blobs denote the pion form factor. The short-dashed line indicates that the intermediate-state pion is taken on-shell.

The SD contributions are subsumed into $S_{\text{EW}}^{\pi\pi} = 1 + 2\alpha/\pi \log \frac{MZ}{m_\tau} + \dots = 1.0233(3)(24)$ [23–30], where the uncertainty reflects the $\mathcal{O}(\alpha/\pi)$ scheme ambiguity pointed out in Ref. [12]. $f_+(s)$ denotes the pion form factor in the charged current, normalized as $f_+(0) = 1$, and radiative corrections are expressed in terms of the factor

$$G_{\text{EM}}(s) = \frac{\int_{t_{\text{min}}(s)}^{t_{\text{max}}(s)} dt D(s, t) [1 + 2f_{\text{loop}}(s, t) + g_{\text{rad}}(s, t)]}{\int_{t_{\text{min}}(s)}^{t_{\text{max}}(s)} dt D(s, t)}, \quad (2)$$

which is the central object of this study. It is normalized in such a way that $G_{\text{EM}}(s) = 1 + \mathcal{O}(\alpha)$, and amounts to averaging the amplitudes $f_{\text{loop}}(s, t)$, $g_{\text{rad}}(s, t)$ for virtual and real contributions, respectively, over the entire phase space (PS). In practice, we perform the calculation of $G_{\text{EM}}(s)$ in the isospin limit, as otherwise a large number of second-order IB effects would need to be considered, and restore the correct phase-space boundaries by mapping $[(M_\pi + M_{\pi^0})^2, m_\tau^2]$ linearly onto $[4M_\pi^2, m_\tau^2]$ in the end [31].

2 Virtual and real corrections

The virtual corrections in ChPT are shown in Fig. 1. In particular, adding self-energy and contact-term contributions, this leads to a chiral prediction $f_{\text{loop}}^{\text{ChPT}}(t)$ that is UV finite but IR divergent, with the latter divergences to be canceled by real radiation. The validity of the resulting prediction for $G_{\text{EM}}(s)$, however, is limited to the low-energy region, as the physics of hadronic resonances is only reproduced perturbatively or integrated out in the low-energy constants (LECs).

This limitation can be overcome in a dispersive approach, in which case the diagrams in Fig. 1 need to be reinterpreted as unitarity diagrams. From this perspective, only diagram (a) needs to be considered further. Keeping in mind that the $\tau\nu_\tau\pi\pi^0$ vertex arises from integrating out the W boson, this topology then takes the form shown in Fig. 2. Following the strategy of Ref. [32], the calculation can be reduced to standard one-loop Passarino–Veltman functions B_0 , C_0 , D_0 [33] by inserting a dispersive representation of the pion form factor

$$f_+(s) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{4M_\pi^2}^{\infty} ds' \frac{\text{Im} f_+(s')}{s' - s} \quad (3)$$

and interpreting the Cauchy kernel as a propagator in the loop calculation. In particular, using an unsubtracted dispersion relation (3) ensures that the result $f_{\text{loop}}^{\text{disp}}(s, t)$ is manifestly UV finite.

Figure 3: Left: global fit to the $\tau \rightarrow \pi\pi\nu_\tau$ spectrum, including the data sets from Belle [16], ALEPH [17, 18], CLEO [19], and OPAL [20]. Right: final result for $G_{\text{EM}}(s)$ and comparison to previous work, and using ChPT instead of dispersion relations for the box diagram (based on Refs. [4, 5]).

The dispersive calculation of $f_{\text{loop}}^{\text{disp}}(s, t)$ does not yet account for the ChPT diagrams besides Fig. 1(a), but due to the absence of any nontrivial analytic structure in the remaining ones, the full result can be constructed by matching at $s = t = 0$:

$$f_{\text{loop}}^{\text{full}}(s, t) = f_{\text{loop}}^{\text{disp}}(s, t) - f_{\text{loop}}^{\text{disp}}(0, 0) + f_{\text{loop}}^{\text{ChPT}}(0), \quad (4)$$

which, as an added benefit, suppresses the high-energy part of the dispersive integral and thus reduces the sensitivity to the asymptotic form of $\text{Im} f_+(s)$.

Finally, to produce numerical results we need to choose a value for the chiral LECs X_ℓ [34], on which the final correction depends linearly. We choose $\bar{X}_\ell(M_\rho) = 14 \times 10^{-3}$ [35], while emphasizing that this is the place at which the scheme ambiguity in $S_{\text{EW}}^{\pi\pi}$ resurfaces, so that only the product $S_{\text{EW}}^{\pi\pi} G_{\text{EM}}(s)$ becomes scale and scheme independent at the considered order.

For the real corrections we follow the general strategy from Refs. [4, 5], including radiation off the τ and the charged pion, resonance contributions that saturate the LECs L_9, L_{10} [36, 37], and the prediction from the Wess–Zumino–Witten (WZW) anomaly [38, 39]. The leading corrections from Low’s theorem [40] can be given in an analytic form, while the remainder has to be calculated numerically. In contrast to the leading Low contribution, which only diverges logarithmically at threshold, it behaves as $G_{\text{EM}}(s) \propto 1/(s - 4M_\pi^2)$, in such a way that a stable numerical evaluation becomes challenging close to threshold. This issue can be circumvented by a suitable change of integration variables [2], which allows us to evaluate both real and virtual contributions down to threshold in a robust manner.

The resonance contributions considered here, in the notation of Refs. [41, 42], can be expressed in terms of two vector couplings F_V, G_V , one axial-vector coupling F_A , and the mass parameters M_V, M_A . In particular, for the couplings we considered: SD constraints [41] ($F_V = \sqrt{2}F_\pi, G_V = \frac{F_\pi}{\sqrt{2}}, F_A = F_\pi$), and data-driven determinations ($F_V \simeq 0.16 \text{ GeV}, G_V \simeq 0.065 \text{ GeV}, F_A \simeq 0.12 \text{ GeV}$), obtained from $\rho \rightarrow e^+e^-, \rho \rightarrow \pi\pi, K^* \rightarrow K\pi$ [43] and $a_1 \rightarrow \pi\gamma$ [44], respectively.

3 Fits to the τ spectral function and consequences for a_μ

For the numerical evaluation of $f_{\text{loop}}^{\text{disp}}(s, t)$, we need input for $\text{Im} f_+(s)$, which should be determined in a self-consistent way with the data for the τ spectral function to which $G_{\text{EM}}(s)$ is applied. To achieve this, we employ an iterative procedure, starting from an Omnès function [45], and calculate a first approximation for $G_{\text{EM}}(s)$. We then use the resulting correction in a fit of $f_+(s)$ to the τ data to obtain an improved $f_+(s)$. We recalculate $G_{\text{EM}}(s)$ with it and iterate the procedure until it converges after a few steps.

	$G_{\text{EM}}^{\text{Low}}$	$G_{\text{EM}}^{\text{rad}}$	$G_{\text{EM}}^{\text{full}}$	PS	$S_{\text{EW}}^{\pi\pi}$	Sum	Full	\tilde{a}_μ
Belle	-2.292(15)(14)	-5.21(3)(2)	-5.44(3)(40)	-7.74(4)(3)	-12.180(57)(8)	-25.36(12)(44)	-24.84(12)(39)	510.1(2.4)(0.2)
Belle+ALEPH	-2.279(13)(16)	-5.20(3)(2)	-5.43(3)(40)	-7.73(4)(3)	-12.177(57)(7)	-25.34(12)(44)	-24.82(12)(39)	510.0(2.4)(0.2)
All	-2.267(13)(14)	-5.19(3)(2)	-5.41(3)(40)	-7.74(4)(3)	-12.166(56)(8)	-25.32(12)(44)	-24.80(12)(39)	509.5(2.4)(0.2)

Table 1: Summary of corrections to $a_\mu^{\text{HVP, LO}}[\pi\pi, \tau]$ in units of 10^{-10} . The first/second error refers to the experimental/theoretical uncertainty.

For the fit we use a form that combines the dispersive representation developed for $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ [13, 46] with explicit resonance contributions for ρ' , ρ'' [47–50]:

$$f_+(s) = \left[1 + G_{\text{in}}^N(s) + \sum_{V=\rho', \rho''} c_V \mathcal{A}_V(s) \right] \Omega_1^1(s), \quad (5)$$

where the phase shift is parameterized as the solution of the Roy equations [51–53], $G_{\text{in}}^N(s)$ denotes a conformal polynomial with threshold $s_{\text{thr}} = (M_\pi + M_\omega)^2$, and the explicit form for \mathcal{A}_V reads

$$\mathcal{A}_V(s) = \frac{s}{\pi} \int_{s_{\text{thr}}}^{\infty} ds' \frac{\text{Im} \mathcal{A}_V(s')}{s'(s'-s)}, \quad \text{Im} \mathcal{A}_V(s) = \text{Im} \frac{1}{M_V^2 - s - i\sqrt{s}\Gamma_V(s)}, \quad (6)$$

where the energy dependence of the width $\Gamma_V(s)$ is constructed from the $\pi\omega$ PS. Here, we use one parameter of $G_{\text{in}}^N(s)$ to ensure P -wave behavior of $\text{Im} f_+(s)$, and a second parameter to enforce the sum rule $1 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{4M_\pi^2}^{\infty} ds' \frac{\text{Im} f_+(s')}{s'}$, which, in the unsubtracted form (3), is mandatory to respect charge conservation. Finally, for the fit at each step we employ yet another iteration to avoid D'Agostini bias [54, 55], and account for the finite bin size via a weighted average [46].

We perform fits for $N = 3, 4, 5$ to the Belle data only, to Belle+ALEPH, and to all data sets combined. We take the global fit as our final result, but we still find it instructive to compare to fits to the more complete data sets only, see Fig. 3(left). Based on these fits, we obtain the result for $G_{\text{EM}}(s)$ in Fig. 3(right). For small values of s close to threshold, our result agrees with ChPT, while significant changes are observed in the vicinity of the ρ resonance. These changes are due to the structure-dependent virtual corrections from Fig. 2, and the corresponding increase in the ρ region has immediate consequences for the a_μ integral.

To quantify the impact on IB corrections to a_μ , we use the master formula

$$\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP, LO}}[\pi\pi, \tau]_{r_{\text{IB}}} = \left(\frac{\alpha m_\mu}{3\pi} \right)^2 \int_{4M_\pi^2}^{m_\tau^2} ds \frac{\hat{K}(s)}{4s^2} [r_{\text{IB}}(s) - 1] v_\tau(s), \quad (7)$$

with $v_\tau(s) = S_{\text{EW}}^{\pi\pi} [\beta_{\pi\pi^0}]^3 |f_+(s)|^2 G_{\text{EM}}(s)$, and where $r_{\text{IB}}(s) = \{1/G_{\text{EM}}(s), (\beta_{\pi\pi}/\beta_{\pi\pi^0})^3, 1/S_{\text{EW}}^{\pi\pi}\}$ for the three τ -specific IB contributions. Our results for the three fit variants are summarized in Table 1, where we also show the breakdown for the leading Low contribution, $G_{\text{EM}}^{\text{Low}}(s)$, and the full radiation off τ and π without resonance or WZW effects, $G_{\text{EM}}^{\text{rad}}(s)$ (the latter are included in $G_{\text{EM}}^{\text{full}}(s)$). Moreover, we give the sum of the three contributions, the full correction without linearization, as well as a quantity \tilde{a}_μ defined by $r_{\text{IB}}(s) = 1 + (\beta_{\pi\pi}/\beta_{\pi\pi^0})^3/[G_{\text{EM}}(s)S_{\text{EW}}^{\pi\pi}]$. First, the differences among the fit variants are very small, owing to the small overall size of the IB corrections. Second, at the relevant level of precision the linearization of IB corrections is not justified, as $\mathcal{O}(e^4)$ terms enhanced by the threshold singularity of $G_{\text{EM}}(s)$, see Fig. 3, are sizable, emphasizing the importance of a stable numerical implementation down to threshold. While the overall uncertainty is dominated by the scheme dependence in the SD contribution, the remaining uncertainty due to radiative corrections mainly reflects the role of higher intermediate states in the real and virtual contributions. Overall, the uncertainty due to $G_{\text{EM}}(s)$ has been reduced by almost a factor of three over the previously assigned error in Ref. [12], with a shift in central value by about 2.5σ .

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